

RagaLoRA: LoRA-Tuning a Diffusion Music Model for Indian Genres

Varun Chawla
Independent Researcher
varunc.7633@gmail.com

Abstract—Text-to-music models today are trained almost entirely on Western music. They do not understand ragas, talas, or the ornamentation central to Indian traditions, and they produce generic output when prompted for Indian genres. This paper describes RagaLoRA, a LoRA adapter that tunes ACE-Step 1.5’s Diffusion Transformer decoder to generate Indian music across ten genres—Hindustani classical, Carnatic, Bollywood, qawwali, ghazal, bhajan, and four more. The adapter is rank-16, weighs 44 MB, touches 11 M of the model’s 2.4 B parameters (0.46%), and trains on 250 balanced samples drawn from a 2,787-segment corpus of Creative Commons and public domain Indian recordings. In A/B tests against the unmodified base model, the adapter shifts outputs in genre-appropriate directions: classical and devotional genres get darker and slower (spectral centroid drops up to 16%, tempo drops up to 35%), while dance and rock genres get louder (RMS energy rises up to 38%). Five of the ten evaluated genres had zero dedicated training data, yet still show coherent shifts, pointing to transfer across related Indian styles. No prior LoRA adapter for a diffusion music model has targeted Indian music at this breadth.

Index Terms—music generation, Indian music, LoRA, diffusion transformer, raga, fine-tuning

I. Introduction

Text-to-music models have gotten remarkably good at Western pop, rock, classical, and electronic music [1], [4], [5]. Ask them for a Hindustani classical piece or a qawwali, though, and the results are underwhelming. Mehta et al. [2] quantify the problem: roughly 86% of dataset hours in music AI research come from the Global North, and genres from the Global South make up just 14.6% of training data.

Indian music is not simply Western music with different instruments. A few properties make it especially hard for models trained on Western corpora:

- Ragas define which notes to use, how to ascend and descend through them (aroha/avaroha), which notes to stress (vadi/samvadi), and which short phrases identify the raga (pakad). The Hindustani system alone has several hundred.
- Talas organize rhythm into cycles of varying length—teentaal has 16 beats, jhaptaal has 10—with subdivision patterns that do not map onto Western time signatures.
- Ornamentation carries structural melodic information. In Carnatic music these techniques are called gamaka; in Hindustani, alankar. They include meend

(glides between notes), kan (grace notes), and andolan (slow oscillations). Stripping them out destroys the raga’s identity.

- Diversity: “Indian music” is an umbrella covering Hindustani and Carnatic classical, Bollywood film songs, Sufi qawwali, Urdu ghazal, devotional bhajan, and modern indie Hindi pop—genres with little in common beyond geography.

The only prior attempt at Indian music generation that I found is GaMaDHaNi [3], which models Hindustani vocal melodies through a two-stage pipeline of pitch contour generation followed by audio synthesis. It targets a single tradition and does not take text prompts.

RagaLoRA takes a different angle: rather than building from scratch, I attach a small LoRA adapter to ACE-Step 1.5 [1], a 2.4 B-parameter text-to-music model, and train it on Indian music so the existing model learns to produce Indian-sounding output. Concretely:

- 1) I built a 2,787-segment dataset across five Indian genre categories from openly licensed recordings.
- 2) I trained a rank-16 LoRA adapter on ACE-Step’s DiT decoder (11 M trainable parameters, 0.46% of the total) using 250 balanced samples over 10 epochs.
- 3) I ran A/B evaluations on ten genres, measuring timbral, tempo, and energy shifts between the base model and the adapted model.
- 4) All weights, training code, and the dataset are publicly available.

II. Background and Prior Art

A. Music Generation Models

MusicGen [4] generates music through a single autoregressive language model with an efficient codebook interleaving strategy, avoiding the cascaded stages typical of earlier systems. Stable Audio [5] brings latent diffusion to audio by adding start-time and duration embeddings, allowing variable-length generation. MusicLM [6] conditions a hierarchical sequence-to-sequence model on joint audio-text embeddings from MuLan. ACE-Step 1.5 [1] pairs a language-model planner with a 24-layer Diffusion Transformer (DiT) renderer, using 8-step distillation for fast inference. All four were trained on predominantly Western data.

TABLE I
LoRA Adapter Configurations

Parameter	Single-Genre	Combined
Rank (r)	8	16
Alpha (α)	16	32
Dropout	0.1	0.1
Target modules	q/k/v/o_proj	
Trainable params	≈ 5.5 M	≈ 11 M
% of total	0.23%	0.46%
Adapter size	22 MB	44 MB

TABLE II
Training Data by Genre Category

Genre Category	Total Segments	Used
Hindustani Classical	1,063	50
Bollywood	728	50
Qawwali / Sufi	455	50
Ghazal	269	50
Bhajan	272	50
Total	2,787	250

B. Computational Analysis of Indian Music

The CompMusic project [9] built research corpora and analysis tools for non-Western music, including raga recognition and melodic analysis for Indian traditions. The compIAM toolkit [10] packages raga detection, tala analysis, and tonic identification for Indian art music into a Python library. The Saraga dataset [11] provides roughly 96 hours of annotated Indian classical recordings (108 Hindustani, 249 Carnatic).

On the generation side, almost nothing exists. GaMaD-HaNi [3] is the closest: it learns to produce Hindustani vocal pitch contours and then synthesizes audio from those contours, but it works within a single classical tradition and was not designed for text-conditioned multi-genre generation.

C. LoRA

LoRA [7] sidesteps full fine-tuning by adding small trainable low-rank factors to frozen weight matrices. Given a pretrained matrix $W_0 \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times k}$, it learns $\Delta W = BA$ with $B \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times r}$, $A \in \mathbb{R}^{r \times k}$, and $r \ll \min(d, k)$. The original weights stay frozen; only A and B are updated. This idea has since been adapted to diffusion models [8] and is built into ACE-Step 1.5’s codebase, which I use directly.

III. Method

A. Base Model

ACE-Step 1.5 has three pieces: (1) a Language Model that turns user prompts into structured generation plans (BPM, key, section layout) through chain-of-thought reasoning; (2) a DiT Decoder with 2.4B parameters across 24 transformer layers that denoises audio latent codes, decoded by a pretrained VAE to 48kHz stereo; and (3) a Text Encoder (Qwen3-Embedding-0.6B [14]) that embeds captions and lyrics. I inject LoRA into the DiT decoder’s attention projections (W_Q, W_K, W_V, W_O) across all 24 layers.

B. Adapter Setup

C. Training Details

Optimizer: AdamW [13], learning rate 1×10^{-4} , linear warmup over 200 steps. Batch size 1, gradient accumulation 4 (effective batch 4). Weight decay 0.01, gradient clipping at 1.0, BFloat16 mixed precision. I ran 10 epochs

(600 optimizer steps total), saving checkpoints every 2 epochs and tracking the best by epoch-level loss. A 5% validation split was configured but too small (roughly 12 samples) to draw conclusions from. Hardware: Apple Silicon MPS with 128 GB unified memory.

D. Preprocessing

Audio is VAE-encoded in tiles; captions and lyrics go through Qwen3-Embedding and then through the DiT’s condition encoder. Text conditioning uses ACE-Step’s SFT_GEN_PROMPT template.

IV. Dataset

A. Sources

All data comes from openly licensed material:

- Saraga [11]: I processed 1,063 Hindustani classical segments from these recordings.
- Internet Archive: Creative Commons and pre-1927 public domain Indian music.
- YouTube Creative Commons: CC-BY recordings found via genre-specific queries.

Everything was resampled to 48kHz stereo WAV and sliced into 30–120 second segments (minimum 10 seconds).

B. Genre Breakdown

I sampled 50 segments per category so no genre would dominate. The training config lists ten genre labels (including sub-genres like bollywood_ballad, sufi_rock, filmi_instrumental), but the data is organized into five categories. At evaluation time, I test all ten labels, so five of them measure generalization to sub-genres the adapter never saw as separate categories.

C. Captions

Each segment gets a genre-aware caption built from templates that use Indian instrument names (sitar, tabla, harmonium, tanpura, sarangi), mood words (meditative, passionate, devotional), and structural markers (alap, gat, taan for Hindustani classical; pallavi, anupallavi for Carnatic; verse/chorus for popular genres). BPM is detected with librosa [12].

TABLE III
Training Loss (Combined Adapter, Epoch-Level Averages)

Epoch	Avg Loss	New Best?
1	0.2399	✓
2	0.1918	✓
3	0.1818	–
5	0.1770	✓
7	0.1762	✓
8	0.1739	–
10	0.1755	–

V. Experiments

A. Training Runs

I trained three adapters: (1) Indian Classical ($r=8$, on 1,063 segments), (2) Bollywood ($r=8$, on 728 segments), and (3) Combined Indian ($r=16$, on the 250 balanced samples above, 600 optimizer steps total). The combined adapter took about 2.8 hours on Apple Silicon MPS.

B. Convergence

Loss drops from 0.2399 to 0.1739 over 10 epochs (a 27.5% reduction) and largely flattens after epoch 5. The best checkpoint was saved at epoch 7 (loss 0.1762). With only 250 training samples and a negligible validation split, I cannot rule out some degree of memorization, though the plateau is consistent with convergence.

C. Evaluation Setup

Ten genre-specific prompts, each with a fixed caption, lyrics, random seed (42), and inference settings. For every prompt, I generate two outputs: one with the base model (LoRA layers disabled via PEFT’s `disable_adapter_layers()`) and one with the adapter active (scale 0.8). Of the ten genres, five have dedicated training data (Hindustani classical, Bollywood, qawwali, ghazal, bhajan); the other five (Carnatic classical, indie Hindi, Sufi rock, filmi dance, Hinglish pop) have none, and test zero-shot transfer.

I extract four metrics with `librosa`: estimated tempo (BPM), dominant chroma pitch class (what I call “tonic” below, though see the caveat in Section VI), mean spectral centroid, and mean RMS energy. All base/LoRA pairs produce different audio files, confirmed by MD5 hash comparison.

D. A/B Results

E. What Changed

1) Tempo: The base model locks onto 172 BPM for 6 out of 10 genres, which points to a strong single-tempo prior in the pretrained weights. After fine-tuning, tempos spread out: Hindustani classical drops to 117 BPM (the prompt specified an alap section, which in practice is performed without a fixed pulse; the slower tempo is at least a step in the right direction, though BPM is a crude proxy for alap’s free-rhythm character). Bhajan drops to

123 BPM, Sufi rock to 112 BPM, filmi dance to 117 BPM. Bollywood ballad speeds up slightly, and ghazal jumps 30% (from 86 to 112 BPM).

2) Brightness: Classical and devotional genres consistently get darker (lower spectral centroid). The biggest shift is Carnatic classical: 1119 \rightarrow 942 Hz, a 15.8% drop. This is consistent with the lower-register timbres of instruments like veena and mridangam that dominate Carnatic recordings. Bhajan drops 6.9%, Bollywood ballad drops 6.3%. On the other side, modern genres get brighter: indie Hindi rises 6.4%, Hinglish pop 4.6%—consistent with the crisp, compressed production typical of contemporary Indian pop.

3) Loudness: The energy shifts are the most striking result. Filmi dance gains 38% in RMS energy—appropriate for a genre built around high-energy dance floors. Sufi rock gains 19%, Bollywood ballad 17%, Hinglish pop 16%. Meanwhile, contemplative genres quiet down: Carnatic classical loses 17%, bhajan loses 15%, qawwali loses 12%. The base model does not make these distinctions.

4) Qawwali: Qawwali’s energy decrease may seem counterintuitive, since live qawwali is often ecstatic and loud. But the training data likely skews toward devotional studio recordings—the quieter side of the genre—rather than the kinetic, clap-driven performances of a dargah. The 12% drop in centroid (1584 \rightarrow 1392 Hz) does fit: qawwali relies heavily on harmonium and deep male vocals, both warm-toned instruments.

F. Summary of Shifts

Loud genres get louder; quiet genres get quieter and warmer. The base model treats all ten prompts similarly. Five of the ten genres tested had no training data at all, yet they still shift in coherent directions, which means the adapter transfers to related Indian styles it never explicitly trained on.

VI. Discussion

A. What Worked

A 44MB adapter—less than half a percent of the model—is enough to push outputs in genre-specific directions. The fact that it works at all on five genres with no dedicated training data is evidence that ACE-Step’s latent space already encodes enough musical structure for a small nudge to redirect it toward Indian conventions.

B. What Did Not

There is a long list of things I did not validate, and any of them could undermine the results above:

No listening tests. Spectral centroid and RMS energy are signal-level statistics. A lower centroid does not guarantee the output sounds like Carnatic music to a trained ear. Listening studies with Indian musicians are needed before making claims about quality or authenticity.

No standard distance metrics. Fréchet Audio Distance (FAD) against a corpus of real Indian recordings would

TABLE IV

Base ACE-Step 1.5 vs. RagaLoRA (rank-16, scale 0.8). Centroid = mean spectral centroid, a rough proxy for brightness. Tonic = dominant chroma class, not a claim about raga key centers (see Section VI). Genres with † had no dedicated training data.

Genre	Tonic		Tempo (BPM)		Centroid (Hz)		RMS Energy	
	Base	LoRA	Base	LoRA	Base	LoRA	Base	LoRA
Hindustani Classical	E	E	172	117	1214	1208	0.099	0.098
Bollywood Ballad	D	B	144	152	1231	1153	0.103	0.120
Qawwali	E	E	172	172	1584	1392	0.130	0.114
Ghazal	E	E	86	112	1284	1347	0.116	0.129
Bhajan	D	B	152	123	1200	1117	0.122	0.103
Indie Hindi†	D	D	117	117	1097	1167	0.128	0.139
Carnatic Classical†	E	B	172	172	1119	942	0.087	0.072
Sufi Rock†	E	E	172	112	2278	2155	0.127	0.151
Filmi Dance†	B	B	172	117	2352	2178	0.131	0.180
Hinglish Pop†	G	E	172	172	1785	1867	0.138	0.160

TABLE V
Direction of Metric Shifts by Genre

Metric	Went Up	Went Down
Energy	Filmi Dance (+38%), Sufi Rock (+19%), Bollywood (+17%)	Carnatic (-17%), Bhajan (-15%), Qawwali (-12%)
Centroid	Indie Hindi (+6%), Ghazal (+5%), Hinglish (+5%)	Carnatic (-16%), Qawwali (-12%), Bhajan (-7%)
Tempo	Ghazal (+30%)	Sufi Rock (-35%), Hindustani (-32%), Bhajan (-19%)

be a much stronger evaluation than the feature-level comparisons reported here.

Tiny dataset, no meaningful validation split. Two hundred fifty training samples is not much. The config included a 5% validation split, but 12 samples is too few to be informative. I cannot confidently separate learning from memorization.

No raga conformance check. I tried running compIAM’s raga detector on the generated classical outputs, but it returned null for every sample. Whether the generated Hindustani pieces actually follow raga grammar—correct aroha/avaroha, proper vadi/samvadi emphasis—is unknown.

Tonic caveat. Indian musicians use a movable-do system where “Sa” can be any absolute pitch. The chroma-based “tonic” I report is just the loudest pitch class in the spectrogram, not a musically meaningful key assignment. It should not be over-interpreted.

Cultural questions. Generating sacred music (bhajan, qawwali) with AI, without input from the communities those traditions belong to, raises questions about cultural authority that go beyond what a technical paper can resolve. I flag this as an open issue.

C. Where This Could Go

The same recipe—small LoRA adapter on a pretrained music model—should work for Arabic maqam, Turkish

makam, gamelan, or any tradition with enough openly licensed recordings. Evaluation would benefit from plugging in tradition-specific analysis tools (compIAM for Indian music, for example) rather than relying on generic spectral features. And future foundation models should include non-Western music in their pretraining data from the start, rather than relying on post-hoc patches like this one.

VII. Conclusion

RagaLoRA shows that a small LoRA adapter on ACE-Step 1.5 can push its output toward Indian music. Classical outputs get darker and slower; Bollywood and dance tracks get louder. Whether these shifts translate into music that Indian listeners would actually recognize as authentic is an open question—one that needs listening tests, not spectrograms. Code, weights, and data are all public.¹

Acknowledgments

Thanks to the Saraga dataset team, the Internet Archive, and the creators of Creative Commons Indian music recordings. This work builds on ACE-Step 1.5 and the PEFT library.

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¹Adapter weights and evaluation data: <https://huggingface.co/veeceeey/RagaLoRA-indian-music-ace-step>

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